

FEATURES OF LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY IN ACUTE CALCULATED CHOLECYSTITIS

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Purpose of research: development of a laparoscopic cholecystectomy method with interpretation of inflammatory changes in the gallbladder in acute destructive cholecystitis.

Materials and methods. The results of performing LCHE in 62 patients with destructive changes are presented. The implementation methodology is described, and a conclusion is made about the high effectiveness of the laparoscopic cholecystectomy methods developed in the clinic.

Of the 62 patients with acute destructive cholecystitis, 19 were operated on urgently within the first 2 hours after admission, 7 due to local and diffuse peritonitis. The vast majority of patients with acute destructive cholecystitis (43 (69.3%)) underwent emergency surgery. Out of 62 patients, 43 (69.3%) underwent surgery urgently, on the first 3 days after admission, and 18 (29%) underwent surgery on the 4th day after admission. We optimized the laparoscopic cholecystectomy technique by combining the methods known to date. The first stage is the aspiration of the gallbladder contents. After aspiration, the gallbladder with its infiltrated wall becomes more mobile, creating conditions for gallbladder traction. The second stage is the mobilization of the cystic artery. Oren.

Results and discussion. After the introduction of improved LCHE methodology technology into clinical practice, since 2015, the conversion rate has decreased to 2%, and since 2000, and to date, it has been 0.4%.

Conclusions. The developed clear technical methods for performing laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LCE) in destructive forms of acute calculous cholecystitis will allow achieving high positive results while maintaining a stable rate of complications at 1-2% and reducing mortality to -0.1%.

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